

The mystery of the Nur al-'Ayn diamond

The Nur al-'Ayn is one of the most important and mysterious gems in the crown jewels of Iran. With no historical accounts of the stone in existence, its story is a mystery. Anna Malecka investigates whether the stone really was cut and polished in Persia during the Qajar dynasty, and traces its route through history.

The Nur al-'Ayn (also written as Noor-ul-Ain), or 'The Light of the Eye', is an oval pink brilliant-cut diamond of approximately 60 ct (the weight of the stone is impossible to calculate exactly without removing it from its holder), making it one of the largest pink diamonds in the world, and is one of the most important gems among the crown jewels of Iran. It is set in a platinum tiara adorned with white, yellow and pink diamonds, which is housed in the Treasury of National Jewels in Tehran, Iran. This is a modern creation, made by the famous American jeweller Harry Winston in 1958 for the wedding of Mohammad Reza Shah Pahlavi and Farah Diba. The Nur al-'Ayn first ignited the interest of Western researchers

in the 1960s. According to V.B. Meen and A. Douglas Tushingham, the Canadian gemmologists who analyzed the gem at the time, the stone is part of the famous historic diamond which appeared on the market in Golconda, India, in 1642. This stone, known as the 'Great Table', was described in the work of Jean-Baptiste Tavernier, the famous French diamantaire and explorer of India. Tavernier described the weight of the Table as 176 1/8 of a *mangelin*, which is around 248 metric ct (Tavernier, 1681). In fact, according to credible accounts by gemmologists, the gem weighed over 300 ct. A second, much larger fragment of the Table is the Darya-ye Nur, or 'Sea of Light' diamond, weighing

around 185 ct, which also currently resides in the Treasury of National Jewels, Tehran.

Having established the origin of both stones, Meen and Tushingham set to wondering what circumstances may have led to the Great Table being divided (Meen and Tushingham, 1968). They speculated that it may have been in Iran shortly before 1834, when the Darya-ye Nur was inscribed with the name of Persia's ruler, Fath Ali Shah. They also accepted that the Light of the Eye may have been created many years later.

The cutting of this gem also bothered Lord Ian Balfour, the famous writer on historic diamonds, who maintained that this stone may have been prepared during the reign of Naser-al-din Shah of Persia. Balfour did not offer anything to back up this assumption, other than mentioning that during the reign of this ruler there were cutting workshops at court, where the stones he acquired in Europe were processed (Balfour, 2009).

Comments which appear in literature concerning the creation of the Nur al-'Ayn are therefore based on speculation, which as far as I know has not been scrutinized on the basis of primary sources. My aim here is to verify these views and establish the true circumstances of the cutting of this diamond, one of the most important in the Persian treasury.

It is highly probable that the Great Table, from which the Nur al-'Ayn gem was taken, came into the possession of the Indian rulers of the Great Mughal dynasty as

The Nur al-'Ayn set in a platinum tiara with white, yellow and pink diamonds, housed in the Treasury of National Jewels in Tehran, Iran. Photo copyright The Royal Ontario Museum.

Great Table' drawing by Jean-Baptiste Tavernier.

early as the seventeenth century. In 1739, the Indian subcontinent was invaded by Persia's Nader Shah, who transported the contents of Delhi's treasury back to the 'Land of the Aryans'. Contrary to the version of events accepted in some works on the topic, the Great Table was not among the valuables (Lee, 2006).

An eighteenth-century Persian author, supports this by stating that the king's loot included a diamond called Nur al-'Uyun, or 'the Light of the Eyes' (Tehrani, AH 1349). This opinion was shared by nineteenth-century Turkish chronicler Ahmed Cevdet Pasa who claimed, on the basis of testament by a historian from the previous century, that Nader Shah brought the Nur al-'Ayn diamond from India, weighing almost 60 ct, and that it then served to decorate his dagger (Cevdet Pasa, 1972-1974; Kesbî, 2002). This would suggest that the Great Table must have been divided up at the Mughal court even before the Persians invaded.

It is also probable that the Mughal lapidaries had cut the major part of the Great Table, Darya-ye Nur. During the two-month Persian occupation of Delhi, the separation of the gem in question would not be possible since it would have required at least 12 weeks of work.

In 1747, the Shah (the then new owner of the Light of the Eye), was murdered. According to Cevdet Pasa, at the moment Nader was killed, the stone was under the supervision of the royal treasurer, after whose death the gem passed into the possession of various Persian nobles. One of them informed a visiting merchant from Istanbul that the diamond's current owner, who had taken possession of it by

violent means, intended to sell the stone. However, due to the nobles' opposition to such valuable items being taken out of Persia, these plans were kept secret. The Istanbulite informed the officials of the Ottoman court about the opportunity to acquire the stone, and they took the decision to have it brought to their capital where it was presented to Sultan Selim III for inspection. The monarch ordered the purchase of the diamond, which involved five months of negotiations resulting in the initial price being reduced from around 4.1 to 1.6 tonnes of pure silver, or 1500 and 600 purses of *akçe* respectively — the chief monetary unit of the Ottoman Empire. The stone was then worked on in the brilliant-cut fashionable among the Ottoman elites of the time.

I have not found any mention of the gem in texts referring to the Turkish treasury during the reign of Selim III. Since it is certain that in 1834 the Nur al-'Ayn belonged to Fath Ali Shah (the earliest information I have found about it in Qajar sources), then at some point between the end of the eighteenth century and that date it must have returned, possibly as a gift, from the Ottoman court to Persia (Rida Quli Mirza, AH 1373).

It is worth mentioning that the craftsmen who Selim III employed as

diamond cutters to prepare the stone in question were Westerners (Cevdet Pasa, 1972-1974). As Europeans and thus the inventors of the art of diamond cutting, they were considered in the entire Islamic world to be the greatest specialists in the industry. They were operating in Muslim courts from the first quarter of the sixteenth century at the latest. However, due to the policy conducted by western commercial companies to protect the mass export of European-cut diamonds eastwards, attempts by oriental royals to employ such specialists were generally extremely difficult and painstaking, and not always successful (Uzunçarsili, 1981; Heeringa, 1910-1952).

Similar problems were encountered by the envoys of Selim III, who were entrusted with employing European diamond workers. After a long search, these emissaries managed to engage two French experts; a certain Monsieur Lison, a Parisian, as well as an unnamed cutter (Jamgocyan, 1990). As there were no other 'Frankish' cutters working at that court, it must have been these men who cut the Light of the Eye in the 1790s.

However, it is worth noting that according to Cevdet Pasa, the Nur al-'Ayn weighed about 60 ct before the processing, whereas the titular gem reached this weight only after its cutting. The same author also mentioned that the stone in question was to be "pyramid-shaped in the uncut form". This, to put it mildly, is not the most precise term to describe the shape of the fragment left after cutting off the Darya from the Great Table. We should also add that the seller of the Light of the Eye bought another rough diamond in Iran which, after cutting in Holland, weighed 20 ct and was also purchased by Selim III.

The Nur al-'Ayn diamond, then, was not cut in Persia around 1834, but at the Ottoman court approximately 40 years earlier. As far as I know, this stone, which has belonged to the Iranian treasury uninterrupted since the first half of the nineteenth century, is the only surviving and documented evidence of the 400 years of Western diamond cutters' presence at Muslim courts.

Portrait of Selim III by John Young, 1815.

Gem and Jewellery History

The mystery of the Nūr al-'Ayn diamond (cont.)

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